
Analysis of the Development of Environmental Social Entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article presents advanced foreign experience in the development of the field of social entrepreneurship, scientists who have conducted research in this area, the emergence of social entrepreneurship in our country, the state of its development today, measures taken to support social entrepreneurship activities, discusses the requirements and procedure for conducting this type entrepreneurial activity.

Key words: social entrepreneurship, register of social enterprises, preferences, environmental entrepreneurship, social project, social goods, renewable energy sources, waste recycling.

Introduction. Entrepreneurship is a constantly growing activity. It is precisely the existing environmental problems that have led to the development of ecological approaches to business activity. Increasing ecological knowledge of the population also increases the need of ecological social entrepreneurs of the society. The limitation of natural resources, the continuous increase of the world's population and the decrease of biological diversity play an important role in the emergence of concerns about ecology. The main difference between social entrepreneurs focused on environmental protection and traditional entrepreneurs is that the main goal is not only to get more profit, but such entrepreneurs strive to create a business model that is environmentally friendly, economically profitable, and creates social value.

Looking at the development of the concept of social entrepreneurship, it can be seen that this concept appeared in the 1980s and has been continuously developing since then. However, despite decades of research and efforts, scientists have not come to a clear conclusion on a comprehensive concept and general definition. Because of this, the dynamic nature of the object and the large number of conceptual objects chosen by the researchers made it impossible to come to a single stop. Many activities related to the development of society and the achievement of high social goals are the basis for the emergence of the concept of modern social entrepreneurship and its popularization among society. Despite the many definitions that exist today, it is difficult to determine a comprehensive definition that can fully classify social entrepreneurship due to the fact that it can be manifested in several forms. In order to determine the importance of the emergence of the concept of social entrepreneurship and the socio-economic development of society, we will consider the scientific ideas and conclusions of scientists in the field.

Methodology. Robert Owen (1771-1858), the founder of the cooperative movement, and Florence Nightingale (1820-1910) are two notable entrepreneurs who established the first official social enterprises and thought about the concept of "social entrepreneurship" at the beginning of the 19th century. The terms "social entrepreneur" and "social entrepreneurship" were first used in the literature in 1953 by Howard Bowen in "Social Responsibilities of Entrepreneurs". These terms were introduced and widely used in the 1980s and 1990s by Bill Drayton, Charles Leadbeater, and

others. From the 1950s to the 1990s, politician Michael Young was a leading promoter of social entrepreneurship¹.

Discussion. Regarding social entrepreneurship, its specific features and general description, major foreign economists H. Bowen, D. Bornstein, J. Elkington, P. Hartigan, B. Drayton, G. Deese, Charles Leadbeater, among modern scientists, J. Boshi, J. Kikal and T. Lyons conducted scientific research.

A.A. Antonova, A.A. Barisheva, B.M. scientists from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). Teplov, M.A. Makarenko, V.V. Kashpur, L.V. Khokhlova, D.M. Shakirova, V.I. Makarevich and others conducted their research on the theoretical and practical problems of social entrepreneurship development and management.

From our local scientists, A.Vahobov, S.Gulomov, U.Gafurov, N.Yuldoshev, N.Makhmudov, A.Soliyev, M.Butaboyev, I.Nosirov, Sh.Zaynutdinov, A.Koshimov, N.Rasulov, N. Norbayev and others conducted research on the entry of social entrepreneurship in our country, its characteristics, ways of managing development, advantages and disadvantages.

The above-mentioned authors have not extensively studied the type of social entrepreneurship based on environmental protection in the scientific research work on the management of the development of social entrepreneurship subjects, and therefore, not enough research has been conducted. The need to solve this problem provides an opportunity to determine the research topic, goals and objectives.

1-rasm. Chiqindini qayta ishlash korxonalarining mahsulot tarkibi bo'yicha ma'lumot²

Analysis. In countries where the type of social entrepreneurship focused on environmental protection is widely developed, social entrepreneurship entities appear in various forms. In our country, ecological social entrepreneurs operate in the fields of collection, removal and sorting of household waste, as well as waste processing. Currently, 51 (30.2%) of the 169 environmental social entrepreneurs in our country are engaged in the provision of household waste collection and sorting services, while the remaining 118 (69.8%) are waste processing enterprises. Almost a third of social business entities performing this type of activity, i.e. 33.1%, go to Tashkent, 14.4% to Fergana, 13.6% to Namangan, 11.9% to Tashkent and 8.5% is the share of Samarkand regions, the regions with the lowest indicators in this regard are Syrdaryo 0%, Kashkadarya 0%, Jizzakh 0.9% and the Republic of Karakalpakstan 0.9%³.

¹ Maxmudov N.M. Narzullayev E.Sh. Structural structure of social entrepreneurship based on environmental protection and its specific features// Journal of Innovations in Social Sciences Volume 1 | Issue 4 (Oct 2021) B-58-65

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³ Statistics Agency Under the President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan

In our study, the share of waste processing enterprises by types of waste processed was also analyzed. According to it, the main part of the existing 118 waste processing enterprises is plastic processing (28), textile waste processing (20), metal waste processing (19), rubber and paper products processing (7 %) areas (Fig. 1).

When the activity of business entities specializing in waste processing in Namangan region, which is the object of the research, was studied, in 2018, the number of business entities in this direction was 17, and "Measures to further improve the management system of work related to household and construction waste" on activities" on the basis of the decision, the number of enterprises on the annexation of territories to business entities on the basis of the principle of public-private partnership has reached 22 (Table 1)⁴.

According to Table 1, waste processing enterprises in the region processed 48,273 tons of waste in 2018 and received 41,514 tons of various products. In 2022, the amount of processed waste increased by 116,157 tons to 164,430 tons. the volume also increased by 83138 tons and made 124652 tons.

Table 1. Economic indicators of business entities specializing in waste processing in Namangan region

№	Indicators	2018 year	2019 year	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year	2022 y. 2018 y. (+;-)
1.	Number of enterprises, pcs	17	17	19	16	22	5
2.	Volume of recycled waste (tons)	48273	76418	104645	119 228	164430	116157
3.	Volume of products from recycling (tons)	41514	68776	89995	100 375	124652	83138
4.	Revenue from the sale of processed products, million soums	266645,4	411749,9	508040,1	664711,1	800642,8	533997
5.	Production costs, million soums	210941,5	300534,7	373256,7	468614,9	544699,6	333758
6.	Profit, million soums	55703,9	111215,2	134783,4	196096,2	255943,3	200239
7.	Rentability, %	20,9	27,0	26,5	29,5	32,0	11,1

If we analyze the financial and economic indicators of business entities specializing in waste processing in the region, the enterprises have achieved positive indicators of economic efficiency in accordance with production. In 2018, the profit of enterprises from the results of their activities amounted to 55703.9 mln. soums, and profitability was 20.9%, in 2022 these indicators will grow accordingly, and the profit will increase by 200,239 million soums to 255,943.3 million soums. soums, the profitability index also increased by 11.1% to 32.0%.

Results. The analyzes show that the establishment and development of business entities specializing in environmental protection is a direction of high socio-economic benefit for the country's economy and environmental protection, as well as for business entities.

When determining the development of business entities specializing in environmental protection, the average arithmetic value of the coefficients of the descriptive indicator of the entity is:

$$I_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n k_o}{n} \quad (1)$$

⁴ Uznature.uz

Here:

k_o – coefficient;

n – the number of indicators in the calculation blog.

$$I_t = (x_i/x - 1) \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda:

I_i - the deviation of the integrated indicator of the subjects of social entrepreneurship in the district;

x_i - the indicator of the social entrepreneurship subject at the district level;

x - is the average value of the integrated indicator of the social enterprise at the district level.

Based on the determined average values, the marginal value norms of the development of social business entities specializing in environmental protection in the cities and districts of Namangan region can be divided into groups using the following table:

Table 2. Marginal value standards for the development of social business entities specializing in environmental protection in cities and districts of Namangan region⁵

No	Specialization of the business entity	Degrees	Threshold amount
1	Social enterprise specializing in environmental protection	Low	$0,1 \leq IT \leq 0,3$
2		Medium	$0,31 \leq IT \leq 0,5$
3		High	$0,51 \leq IT \leq 1,0$

In our research, the marginal value norms of the development of social business entities specializing in environmental protection in the districts of Namangan region were determined by calculating the average arithmetic value of the descriptive indicator coefficients of the subject in determining the development of the activities of business entities specializing in environmental protection. In this case, to determine the deviation of the integral indicator of social entrepreneurship subjects by district, it was achieved by calculating the ratio of the indicator of the social entrepreneurship subject at the district level to the average value of the integral indicator of the social entrepreneurship subject at the district level. From the data in the table, it can be seen that in the districts of Namangan region, the marginal value standards for the development of social business entities specializing in environmental protection are high ($0.51 \leq IT \leq 1.0$), ($0.31 \leq IT \leq 0.5$) divided into groups such as medium and ($0.1 \leq IT \leq 0.3$) low (Table 2).

To evaluate the development of enterprises specializing in environmental protection, the rating and scoring method was used. In this case, the integral indicators are defined as the average sum of the analyzed indicators, the level of significance is determined. Then the color (level) of the indicators was taken from the total evaluation amount in the range of 0.1 to 1.0, and the highest, middle and lowest levels of development were determined. The sum of colors (level) determines the complex amount of indicators. This coefficient is unsatisfactory if it is in the range of 0.1 to 0.3, satisfactory from 0.31 to 0.5, and positive from 0.51 to 1.0, and the higher this indicator is, the higher the economic development of the enterprise. . The development of social business entities specializing in environmental protection operating in the districts of Namangan region and the growth of indicators of the social business entity at the district level are closely related to the socio-economic potential of the region.

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